

SMART ERA PROJECT - EIP AGRI PRACTICE ABSTRACTS

A NEW METHOD OF SMARTNESS ASSESSMENT FOR RURAL AREAS

Poliedra, in cooperation with all project partners, has tried to meet the need of having a **standardised way to assess** the level of smartness, defined as **the level of digital maturity or readiness, of rural and mountain areas**. A standardised norm exists does exist to assess the smartness of cities and communities (namely ISO standard 37122:2019), but **no such norm exists for rural areas**. SESAM's development started from a **literature review** of smartness assessment methods, both qualitative and quantitative, and from the careful evaluation of ISO standard 37122:2019. As a general structure, SESAM has both a **qualitative and a quantitative path**, aiming to clarify the needs and expectations of rural areas in terms of digital transition, and quantifying them. **The project's rural areas have tested SESAM** at different levels, and have found it user friendly and flexible enough for their scope: those who wanted a general overview could make use of only the qualitative path, whereas those who wanted a more thorough assessment could delve more deeply in the evaluation of a selected smartness indicators. SESAM's quantitative path is composed of **six dimensions of smartness**: from **Enabling Factors to Economy**, from **Governance & Policies to Mobility & Transport**, from **Environment & Climate to Services to the populations**. SESAM's qualitative path includes a **survey** on the relevance, for each rural area, of the dimensions listed above, as well as the possibility of emotional mapping, which gauges the emotional response of local populations to various aspects and features of their own area. SESAM has been designed to allow rural and mountain areas to assess, qualitatively and/or quantitatively,

their own level of digital maturity and/or readiness, which help them in setting priorities for their own community-led digital transitions.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

27 different smartness assessment methodologies were assessed and evaluated in the literature review, a key aspect in the creation of SESAM. Moreover, **the evaluation and assessment of ISO standard 37122:2019 was also important**, as it helped understand how a smartness assessment standard was created and works. The partnership thought that SESAM could become an expansion of ISO standard 37122:2019, and if not, a new international standard to gauge and assess the level of digital maturity and readiness of rural and mountain areas.

The possible **obstacles** are mostly connected to the possible **complexity** of SESAM for groups of local stakeholders, and the possible **need for guidance and facilitation** while compiling the quantitative path in particular: this is also the main reason why SESAM also includes a possible more ready to use qualitative path.

ADDITIONAL MATERIALS

[Deliverable 2.1 "Smartness Assessment methodology"](#)

